

DEVELOPMENT OF METAL OXIDE SEMICONDUCTOR GAS SENSOR BASED SYSTEM (E-NOSE) FOR TROPICAL FRUIT SORTING

Ashok Kanade Department of Electronic Science, P.V.P. College, Pravaranagar, India, 413713.

Arvind Shaligram Department of Electronic-Science, Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, India, 411007.

Abstract:

The present work deals with development of electronic Nose using commercially available metal oxide gas sensor array having wide spectrum of VOC combustible gas sensing. The sensor used are non-selective to specific gas as like gas sensing receptors in mammalian nostril. The developed system consists of hardware and software for pattern recognition. The developed systems performance was evaluated for pre-packaging classification of guava fruit nondestructively. Radar plot and principal component analysis (PCA) techniques were used in order to investigate the effectiveness of developed e-nose system for discriminating guava fruit samples in four different ripening states as green, ripe, overripe and spoiled. The radar plot shows different odor signature for different ripening states. The Principle component analysis plot indicates a distinct separation between the four classes. The results suggest that this e-nose system is capable to classify guava fruits and it would be a feasible system to be used in a real scenario.

Keywords: Electronic Nose, Guava fruit, Fruit classification, PCA, Fruit sorting.

1. Introduction:

Packaging of harvested fruits and vegetables is important step in journey from producer to consumer. The handling, transporting and marketing of fresh produce is practiced through bags, crates, baskets, hampers, cartons, bulk bins and palletized containers. The permeability requirement depends upon respiration rate, package bulk density and temperature of the storage. The pre-packaging classification reduces the transportation cost by eliminating unwanted and inedible portion of fruit. Pre-packaging reduces the shopping time of the consumer as the produce is graded before the package. By predicting shelf life at room temperature and refrigerated conditions, pre-packaging helps the grocer to market his produce over a long period and thereby, avoid losses due to spoilage [1]. Conventionally guava fruits classification before packaging has been done by trained human graders according to odor and skin color. But this approach has many disadvantages in terms of objectivity and repeatability. Also a human nose cannot sniff high number of samples because it gets fatigued rapidly with increasing number of samples and also there is possibility of eye disease like color blindness etc. [2]. The failure rate in human grader based classification can be avoided by using electronic classification systems. The electronic classification systems are either destructive or nondestructive types [3]. The conventional fruit classification methods are destructive type in which fruit need to puncture, crush or sliced. In some methods chemicals were applied on fruits for classification, which may danger to human health. Hence such methods are not desirable. For testing firmness of a fruit, a slicing and puncture through Penetrometer will damage the fruit resulting in spoiled produce. Other methods include measuring levels of chemical species; pH, TSS, TTA, ethylene contents, high performance liquid chromatography or gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) requires crushing of fruit for getting pulp or juice [4]. Besides these destructive conventional methods, there are also non destructive techniques which are used. These methods include NMR, PMR, vision system and acoustics. However, all above conventional methods for classification of guava are inconvenient and complicated because they requires specialized skills, are time intensive, labour and are more costly. A simple and reliable method for classification of guava fruits is therefore needed.

Another popular non destructive method for fruit classification is the use of electronic nose. An e-nose system, which is a simple and fast method using a specially designed gas sensors array and suitable pattern recognition techniques to detect and discriminate between complex fruit odors [5].

This paper presents here, how we developed a low-cost application specific portable e-nose system and tests its ability for classification of guava fruit cultivar compared to conventional methods. The classification results confirmed that the developed e-nose system is effective and can tackle many problems associated with the use of human panels. Individual variability, mental state, adaptation, fatigue, infections, subjectivity and exposure to hazardous compounds all parameter taken for consideration. The e-nose can create odor exposure profiles beyond the capabilities of the human panel or GC/MS measurement techniques [6-7]. Consider the demands of multi-target contaminants detection and the low-cost of e-nose, we select eight Figaro Inc. in Japan made TGSxx series MOS gas sensors. The TGSxx series sensors were selected because they have cost-effective, cross sensitive. The main objectives in this study were (1) Evaluate the capacity to measure the change in VOC production of guava fruit during different ripening states in controlled environment using a developed electronic nose device in our laboratory (2) Study Radar plot analysis and principal component analysis (PCA) to obtain whether the developed electronic nose system is able to discriminate between different ripening classes of guava fruits (3) To check prediction performance of developed e-nose system to unknown guava fruit samples using feed forward neural network with back propagation training algorithm.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Design of electronic nose using MOS gas sensors

Figure 1 shows schematic diagram of developed e-nose system that was used for the experimentation. The developed electronic nose system consisting of four functional components that operates serially on an odorant sample; a fruit sample handler called as concentration chamber, an array of eight different MOS gas sensors, a signal conditioning unit and DAQ card connected to laptop which has indigenously developed GUI for data acquisition and pre-processing programmed in LabVIEW2012 software.

The most crucial part of the e-nose is the odor delivery system. The purpose of this system is to transfer the headspace or VOC released by fruit to be analyzed to the gas sensors array. The odor delivery system is designed to measure static response of gas sensor array.

The sensor array is composed of eight metal oxide semiconductor (n-MOS) type chemical sensors. Commercially available tin oxide gas sensors made from Figaro Inc. Japan were chosen to form the chemical sensor array. Table 1 specifies the sensors used in the array and their primary target application gases.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of developed E-nose system

The MOS sensors conductivity changes due to adsorption of molecules in the gas phase, and on subsequent surface reactions. They consist of a ceramic substrate coated by a metal oxide semiconducting film, and heated by a wire resistor. These sensors show a certain degree of affinity towards a specific gas but are sensitive towards a wide spectrum of gas types with overlapping sensitivities. These sensors housed in a stainless steel sensor chamber.

Table 1: E-nose Array sensors and their application gases

Sensor No.	Sensor Model	Target Gas Sensitivity
1,3	TGS2602	VOCs, ammonia, H2S, etc
2	TGS2600	hydrogen, ethanol, etc.
4	TGS2611	Methane
5	TGS2620	Alcohol, Solvent vapors
6	TGS822	Organic Solvent Vapors
7	TGS813	LPG, Methane
8	TGS832	Chlorofluorocarbon

The measuring circuit of each sensor is shown in fig.2. A load resistor is connected in series with each sensor and a common power supply of 5 V is used for both the heater voltage and the voltage applied to the voltage divider formed by the sensors and the load resistances. The voltage across the load resistor was used as response of the sensor.

Figure 2: Unit cell circuit diagram of e-nose sensor array

The relationship between sensor resistance and the concentration of deoxidizing gas can be expressed by the following equation over a certain range of gas concentration:

$$R_s = A[C]^{-\alpha} \quad (1)$$

Where:

R_s = electrical resistance of the sensor

A = constant

[C] = gas concentration

α = slope of R_s curve

2.2 Software for Data acquisition and analysis

The national instruments USB6009 DAQ card and specially developed software GUI for data acquisition was used. DAQ cards 8 analog inputs Channels (A0-A7) were used to acquire analog signals from the sensor array. Developed electronic nose requires various activities for its operation. Many of these activities are repetitive actions that must be scheduled at fixed time intervals. Figure 3 shows a flow diagram representing all the actions necessary to perform a complete measurement cycle

Figure 3: Macro activities in developed e-nose system operation

A complete library of VIs for data acquisition, signal pre-processing, storage, feature extraction, normalization and pattern recognition, instrument control are contained in the developed e-nose software tool. This software is based on state machine technology and programmed in LabVIEW2012. Particular states are available to user for do specific work. Individual buttons are

provided for the particular operation on the main menu VI as shown in Figure 4a. An Exit or Back button on each VI is provided to return to the main menu VI.

Figure 4: a) E-Nose Software main user interface b) Data acquisition interface for odor

In main user interface, user first record the sensor response in air then record the sensor response in odor gas and finally do the pre-processing on stored data. The pre-processed data will be saving for analysis and pattern recognition purpose. The PCA is available for pattern recognition statistically. The user has choice to enter number of samples and sampling time in seconds. The acquired data displayed on waveform graph as time Vs sensor response as shown in fig. 5b. In calibration the voltage response was converted into change in conductance of sensor (G) using below formulas. (2-5)

$$V_o = \frac{R_L}{R_L + R_s} * V_{cc} \quad \dots (2)$$

[V_{cc}=5V constant, R_L=10K constant, V_o=Sensor response in V]

$$R_s = R_L \left[\frac{V_{cc}}{V_o} - 1 \right] \quad \dots (3)$$

R_s=sensor resistance in Ω

$$G = \frac{1}{R_s} \quad \dots (4)$$

[G=Conductance of sensor in Siemens]

Thus sensor array data was calibrated and converted into sensor conductance. After calibration the eight channel data was collected in the form of matrix array and stored in an excel sheet for further processing. The acquired sensor responses were displayed with color codes as voltage and conductance with respect to time on the front panel of VI as shown in fig.4b. The numerical value of the acquired data at a particular instant was also displayed.

Each sensor produces a steady state response which evolves, as the target odor vapor exposed to the sensor array. There are several interfering inputs which affect the responses of the sensor. Drift problem occurs in the pre-processing and the recognition stage. The standard methods applied for data preprocessing is relative response (S) to a target odor. The separate VI is developed for pre-processing accessible from main user interface.

The relative response (S) to a target gas is defined as the ratio of the change in conductance of a sample upon exposure of the gas to the original conductance in air. The relation for S is given as

$$S = \frac{G_{gas} - G_{air}}{G_{air}} \quad (5)$$

Where:

S=Relative response of sensor,

G_{gas}=Conductance of sensor in gas environment, (ref.exp.4)

G_{air}=Conductance of sensor in air environment.

Specificity or selectivity is defined as the ability of a sensor to respond to a certain gas in the presence of different gases.

2.3 Experimental design

The Guava (*Psidium guajava*) fruits of Lucknow 49 type were obtained from the orchard at altitude 504 m, latitude 19.76° north, longitude 74.48° east. Fruits were selected for uniformity of size, color and freedom from blemishes. The trained human grader's service was used for picking the fruit from tree and sorting into four classes as green, ripe, overripe and spoiled. These fruits were selected and sorted according to uniform size, weight and color approximately. The harvested fruits were washed under clean running water and immersed in a 1% sodium hypochlorite solution at 25 °C for 5 minutes for disinfection. After drying the fruits were placed in carton boxes. After drying, the storage was conducted in laboratory condition having controlled environment maintained at a temperature and relative humidity of 26 ± 1 °C and 41 ± 5% respectively.

The experimental design used was completely random (CRD), with 2 treatments to each fruit sample. The experiment consisted of 10 repetitions for each treatment. For training 15 fruits samples of each class were used and it resulted in 300 observations for each class and total 1200 observations for four classes of guava fruit. For validation of trained ANN, 5 fruits samples in each class were used and it resulted into 100 observations per class. All four different ripening state fruits were evaluated

at the picked day (day 0) using developed electronic nose technique.

2.4 Fruit odor analysis procedure using developed hardware and software

The first stage in odor analysis was to flush a fresh air to the sensor array for obtain a baseline. The air response was recorded and stored in excel file for baseline correction. First stage of pre-processing consists of manipulating the sensor response with respect to its baseline (e.g., response to a reference analyte or air) for the purposes of drift compensation, contrast enhancement and scaling.

The fruit sample was placed in an airtight plastic jar called as concentration chamber having volume of 1L and it was equilibrated for 0.5hr. After 0.5hr the headspace reached a steady state and experiments were conducted. The headspace gas was pumped by using centrifugal air pump with air flow-rate 3.2 L/min through a rubber tube and non-return solenoid valves into air tight gas measurement chamber of 0.6 L capacity. The gas reaches over the MOS sensor array placed inside measurement chamber; connected to the signal conditioning unit outside the chamber as shown in fig.1. Airflow always kept constant throughout the measurement for 30 second. Then measurement chamber was locked using solenoid valves and remain steady for 60 second for reaching sensors to its steady state. The electronic valves were controlled by a LabVIEW program, guide the air and headspace as per requirement.

When the sensors exposed by the odorant gas, it produces a transient response as the VOCs interact with the surface and bulk of the sensor's active material. A steady state condition is reached in a few seconds to a few minutes, depending on the sensor type. The odor from guava fruit sample was measured by sensor array for 100 s, the collected data interval was 1 s.

The measurement process is automatically controlled by software that we developed using LabVIEW2012. Samples of each guava fruit cultivar measured twice as per experimental design. Stored data was used for pre-processing to evaluate the sensor array response. Then the sensor housing chamber flushed out for few seconds using vacuum pump suction, so as to remove the odorant mixture from the surface and bulk of the sensor's active material [9]. The main purpose is to clean the chamber, circuits and return sensors to their baseline. By guiding air flow through electronic valves clean air enters the circuit, crosses the measurement chamber first and sucks the remaining volatiles out of the circuit using vacuum pump. The empty concentration chamber was also cleaned using this process. E-nose was operated at the temperature of 24^o C and 40–45% RH during all experiments. The stored data is in the form of matrix array that contains 8 columns related to eight MOS sensors present in the sensor array and no. of rows related to no. of data points. This data was stored in Excel sheet format, which was used for statistical as well as neural network analysis using LabVIEW2012 and Matlab10a software. Figure 5 shows photograph of developed e-nose system and software.

Figure 5: Developed e-nose system photograph

3. Result and Discussion:

The e-nose data was analyzed using radar plot technique shown in fig.6. The different odor signature for distinct class of ripeness was observed from the analysis. The magnitude of each axis indicates the relative response of individual sensor to the fruit odor. A unique odor-print was obtained for four ripening states of guava fruit as green, ripe, overripe and spoiled. This indicates the use of non-specific selective gas sensor arrays to construct an odor database.

Figure 6: Radar plots explaining the discriminating power of developed e-nose for green, ripe, overripe and spoiled class of guava fruits.

The relative response of eight gas sensors were analyzed using PCA and the first two principle components are plotted in fig.7. The discrimination ability of e-nose was tested using PCA analysis. PCA analysis was applied to 400x8 data samples (100x8 data points of each class). The two principal components $\{PC_{1,n}, PC_{2,n}\}$ was obtained and has the two greatest variances: 80.22% and 17.59% (or total cumulative variance of 97.81%) of the variance in the input variables, respectively. The scores of the four groups of fruits was plotted for principal component 2 (PC2) versus principal component 1 (PC1). The discrimination between the four ripening states of guava as green, ripe, overripe and spoiled can be clearly seen from the figure. The processed data show a shift of the different ripening states which coinciding with the classification by trained human graders. The four clusters from left to right indicate the discrimination of fruit classes from green to spoil. A strong pattern separation was found between the four ripening classes of guava. This agrees well with human expert grading results.

Figure 7 Two dimensional PCA plot for the response of sensor array to four ripening classes of guava fruit

The developed system has enough resolution to explain the different ripeness states. Principal components score plot proves the capability of sensor array used in e-nose with significant performance for classification of guava fruits on the basis of their ripening state. It is clearly that e-nose system that we developed, confirming well performance in classification of guava cultivar. The PCA result also showed that the four classes were appropriately separated with high pattern separation in the feature space indicates robustness of this classification system could be confirmed.

4. Conclusion

We have shown that the developed application specific e-nose system is able to classify guava fruit cultivar with high accuracy. The odours of the different ripening state guava cultivar were evaluated using developed e-nose system and were sorted into the same four classes as they were sorted by the human expert; Thus the developed e-nose is effective in discriminating various ripening classes of guava fruits. Thus developed e-nose system may be useful, simple, fast and low-cost method for classification of guava fruits.

In experiment radar plot and PCA based classification successful in separating the fruit samples into four different groups or clusters with adequate accuracy and resolution. The indigenously designed dynamic headspace sampling technique in e-nose

proven to be very useful; signals are stronger because of fruit vapors accumulated long period of time. The results obtained using our developed e-nose determines different ripening state of guava fruit successfully.

References:

- [1] L. R. Verma, Dr. V. K. Joshi, "Postharvest Technology of Fruits and Vegetables: Handling, Processing, Fermentation, and Waste Management, Volume 2", Indus publishing company, 2000
- [2] Kea-Tiong Tang , Shih-Wen Chiu, Chih-Heng Pan, Hung-Yi Hsieh, Yao-Sheng Liang and su-Chieh Liu, "Development of a Portable Electronic Nose System for the Detection and Classification of Fruity Odors", *Sensors* 2010, 10, 9179-9193; doi:10.3390/s101009179
- [3] Ashok Kanade and Dr. A. D. Shaligram, "Development of an e-Nose using metal oxide semiconductor sensors for the classification of climacteric fruits", *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, Volume 5, Issue 2, February-2014, ISSN 2229-5518.
- [4] Rashida E. El Bulk, El Fadil E. Babiker & Abdullahi H. El Tinay, "Changes in chemical composition of guava fruits during development and ripening", *Food Chemistry*, Vol. 59, No. 3, pp. 395-399, 1997
- [5] J. Brezmes, E. Llobet, X. Vilanova, G. Saiz, X. Correig , "Fruit ripeness monitoring using an Electronic Nose", *Sensors and Actuators B* ,69 (2000) 223–229
- [6] Gomez, A. H., Wang, J., Hu, G., & Pereira, A. G. (2006). Electronic nose technique potential monitoring mandarin maturity. *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*, 113(1), 347-353.
- [7] C. Di Natale , A. Macagnano , F. Davide , A. D'Amico , R. Paolesse ,T. Boschi , M. Faccio , G. Ferri , "An electronic nose for food analysis", *Sensors and Actuators B* 44 (1997) 521–526